

FERTILITY OF IRRIGATION SOILS IN FERGHANA REGION AND PROBLEMS OF ITS INCREASE

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Abstract. *The article presents analytical information on the chemical properties, fertility and improvement of irrigated soils in Fergana region. It is noted that the chemical properties of soils are an important factor in the formation of soil fertility indicators.*

Keywords: *fertility, mechanical composition, groundwater, alluvial fan, salinity, automorphic soil, hydromorphic soil, nutrients.*

Introduction. Currently, the main part of irrigated agriculture lands, soils with unfavorable meliorative conditions have been developed and put into operation. In this regard, it is necessary to regularly monitor productivity indicators that are formed in accordance with the meliorative state of these soils.

In particular, in the semi-desert and desert regions located in Fergana Valley, large territories have been developed and are currently widely used.

Due to the long period of exploitation, these soils are currently included in the number of old-irrigated soils, and their properties and characteristics have become similar to the soils used before them. However, although their natural conditions are similar, their properties and characteristics are different, and their use is associated with specific problems and positive situations. To analyze the situation in this regard, we selected soils scattered in the gray and desert areas of the Oltiariksoy and Kuvasoy cones as a research site.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

The works of many research scientists on the study of soil fertility properties are known until today, including those of K. Mirzajonov (56), Zh. Sattorov (2005), B. Musayev (2001), Kh. Ryskieva (1989), T. Zokirov (37), A. Azamov (1980), Y. Kulmurodova (1990).), Z. Askarova (1993), B. Kadyrkhojayev (1986), V. Isakov, U. Mirzayev (2009), Maksudov A. 1974, 1975, 1982; Tozhiboyev S. 1977, 1979; Mirzajonov K. 1979; Komilov O.K., Isakov V.Yu. In 1991, work was carried out by G. Yuldashev (2005), U.B. Mirzaev (2018) and many other research scientists. In these studies, soil fertility and its formation are determined by their agrochemical properties, and changes in the conditions of irrigated agriculture are mainly covered using the example of various soils. According to these researchers, soil fertility changes depending on a number of factors, such as its physical and chemical properties, as well as the fertilization system and its proper organization.

In the process of soil development, a number of changes occur in their cross-section. The direction of the processes occurring in them changes, and under the influence of anthropogenic factors, they change in another direction. At the same time, soil fertility changes, a large part of natural fertility changes and decreases, and soil depletion occurs.

Soil depletion is primarily determined by the amount of humus and other nutrients. Nutrients change in direct proportion to the change in the amount of humus.

In this regard, this issue was also noted by researchers who were conducting research in these regions at that time [1, 2, 3].

Research methodology. In field studies, the method of placing soil sections along a geochemical-geographical section was used. The "Methodological recommendations" of V.V. Dokuchaev from Soil Science Institute were also used. Laboratory analyses were carried out according to the methods specified in the general guidelines developed by E.V. Arinushkina and UzPITI (1977), and the works of A.P. Aleksandrovsky were used to highlight the evolutionary process. Verification and processing of the results of water absorption analysis are based on the works by G. Yuldashev and U. Mirzaev about "Workshops on Soil Chemistry" (2017) and "Laboratory and Practical Classes on Soil Chemistry" (2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Isfayramsoy cone plains, which occupy the central part of Fergana Valley, are subaerial deltas of complex structure. Isfayramsoy, Akbarrovotsoy, Naymansoy and Kuvasoy, emerging from the mountains, are divided into small branches. The networks have formed their own spreading cones and are connected to each other. The western part of the Margilonsoy cone spread is covered by the cone-shaped deposits of Fayziobodsoy, and the eastern part is combined with the Naymansoy and Akbarrovotsoy deposits. Thus, the originality is reflected in the spread of the Oltiariksoy cones.

Due to the high slope of the terrain, the relative lightness of the mechanical composition, the high level of the skeletal structure, the depth of water seepage and the lack of participation in the process of soil formation, the movement of water in the soil is almost one-way - from top to bottom and the head of the cones is light in color. In the cross section of the soil, the matter is not in the accumulation of easily soluble salts in water, but in the speed and high speed of leaching processes being observed. Therefore, the level of soil salinity here is low, almost all soils by the amount of dry residue (0.21-0.28%) belong to the category of non-saline (Table 1).

Only in the upper soil layer a slightly larger amount of hydrocarbonate ions is noticeable (0.015%). The amount of other salts is minimal.

In the lower parts of the cone plains, that is, in the parts belonging to the Central Fergana Desert, you can see a completely different picture. There are two ways of salt accumulation in the soil. Large and small lakes are widespread in the northern lower part of the cone plains, in the lowlands between the cones.

Table 1.

Quantity and composition of water-soluble salts in the soils of the study area (in %)

Section №	Depth, cm.	Dry residue	HCO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺ +K ⁺
Irrigated light gray soils								
1	0-25	0,210	0,009	0,008	0,126	0,028	0,012	0,014
	25-41	0,226	0,010	0,010	0,134	0,031	0,013	0,014
	41-67	0,243	0,010	0,010	0,153	0,037	0,013	0,016
	67-100	0,270	0,012	0,014	0,167	0,044	0,018	0,011
	100-145	0,278	0,015	0,014	0,174	0,045	0,018	0,011
	145-173	0,276	0,015	0,012	0,168	0,043	0,017	0,011
	173-210	0,280	0,014	0,012	0,178	0,043	0,020	0,009
Irrigated meadow-saz soils								

2	0-32	0,253	0,010	0,007	0,161	0,038	0,018	0,007
	32-48	0,399	0,010	0,010	0,260	0,080	0,019	0,006
	48-89	0,504	0,012	0,010	0,321	0,102	0,019	0,010
	89-123	0,540	0,007	0,010	0,362	0,105	0,024	0,017
	123-164	0,532	0,010	0,010	0,350	0,120	0,017	0,010
	164-191	0,556	0,006	0,009	0,378	0,112	0,024	0,014
3	0-30	0,414	0,009	0,010	0,274	0,083	0,018	0,011
	30-44	0,469	0,009	0,012	0,315	0,094	0,020	0,011
	44-67	0,782	0,010	0,012	0,534	0,172	0,028	0,016
	67-114	1,044	0,012	0,015	0,722	0,225	0,042	0,023
	114-150	1,163	0,012	0,015	0,804	0,245	0,050	0,023
	150-171	1,033	0,012	0,012	0,714	0,224	0,039	0,021
	171-183	0,800	0,010	0,010	0,697	0,220	0,038	0,021

The lowlands of these regions also served as a drainage basin for wastewater during the new growing season. At a certain stage in the region's development, these reservoirs lost their flow and turned into salt lakes. The lake "came to life", accumulating sediment, drying up and flooding several times during filling. As a result, saline gypsum and highly saline soil with several distinct gypsum layers in the cross-section of the soil are formed.

The soils of the area of our studies, as already mentioned in the previous works, were developed in different periods, their meliorative state is satisfactory and unsatisfactory. The agrochemical properties of the soils and the process of plant nutrition are intensive and effective in favorable meliorative conditions. Accordingly, in the soils we studied, their nutritional status is not at the same level. Although the soil environment on old-irrigated pale gray soils is good, measures aimed at increasing productivity cannot be considered sufficient (Table 2). Because of this, there is a lack of nutrients in the diet. In other soils, the distribution of nutrients depends on the transverse structure of the soil.

Although the study area differs in automorphic and hydromorphic soil differences, as well as in almost all other main characteristics, it may not differ in agrochemical properties. Because during the period of their use, anthropogenic impact had a consistent effect on maintaining these properties at the same level. However, our studies have shown that there are differences in the agrochemical properties of the soils of the study area, as well as in the morphological structure and chemical properties.

Soils of the head of the cone belong to the category of automorphic soil formations and in the section differ in this respect from the soils of the middle and lower parts. According to our results, the agrochemical properties of these soils are average, we can say that they correspond to the position shown in the existing scientific literature on these soils, and the problem of increasing the amount of nutrients has not yet been sufficiently resolved. According to the results of our studies, these soils are distinguished by unique agrochemical properties. This situation is especially evident in the distribution of the amount of humus, total and mobile nitrogen, mobile phosphorus and exchangeable potassium across the cross-section.

In poor (e.g., rich) soil varieties, the amount of nutrients is distributed across the section, gradually decreasing from top to bottom. They have a deep plant nutrition zone and can absorb nutrients from the lower layers. The amount of humus in the section is about 0.7-1.7%, total nitrogen is about 0.07-0.16%, moderately provided with mobile forms of nutrients. However, in

some soils with geochemical barriers, the distribution of nutrients is uneven and their amount is characterized by a very small amount compared to their total amount. This condition is typical for the soils of Central Fergana cone-spreading soils (section 3).

If we take into account that one of the problems of improving the soil nutrition regime is an increase and moderate amount of their easily soluble - mobile forms, it becomes clear that this situation is an urgent problem in this regard.

Table 2.

Amount of humus and nutrients in the soils of the study area.

Section №	Depth, cm	Humus, %	C:N	Gross forms, %			Mobile forms, mg/kg		
				N	P	K	NO ₃	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
Irrigated light gray soils									
1	0-25	1,00	4,8	0,12	0,13	1,72	19	27	165
	25-41	0,63	5,2	0,07	0,08	1,33	12	13	120
	41-67	0,41	4,7	0,05	0,07	0,79	6	8	54
Irrigated meadow-saz soils.									
2	0-32	1,49	6,2	0,14	0,15	2,00	28	25	194
	32-48	1,17	7,5	0,12	0,11	1,29	15	15	97
	48-89	0,75	4,8	0,09	0,09	0,71	8	8	71
3	0-30	1,82	5,90	0,18	0,17	0,15	21	34	182
	30-44	0,90	4,35	0,08	0,19	1,12	10	11	107
	44-67	0,31	4,50	0,04	0,10	0,63	-	5	34

In general, one of the main and most important goals of conducting agrochemical research is to solve the problems of satisfying the need of plants for nutrients. For this, it is important to study the interaction of the soil macro and plants and their forms.

CONCLUSION

According to the above, the life of cultivated plants is always interconnected with the external environment. Because plants receive the necessary substances for normal growth and development from the external environment. Between plants and the external environment, there is an exchange of substances, in which nutrition from the roots is especially important. In this process, plants absorb various nutrients from the soil along with water under the influence of osmotic pressure through the roots, and the substances obtained, after a series of complex changes based on physical and chemical laws, end up in the composition of plant organs and tissues, and are also spent on their constant renewal. Also, according to the results of the comparison, the problems of soil fertility in the desert region with unfavorable meliorative conditions, compared to light gray soils with relatively favorable meliorative conditions, depend on the level of their salinization.

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